

Ground penetrating radar measurement of snow in Svalbard – past, present, future (SnowGPR)

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1. Introduction

The warming of the Arctic climate, which is well documented (IPCC 2019), causes progressive and ongoing changes in the cryosphere (Box et al. 2018; van Pelt et al. 2019; Schuler et al. 2020; Błaszczuk et al. 2021). The seasonal snowpack, which covers ~60% (summer) to 100% (winter) of the land in Svalbard, is very sensitive to the changing climate (Gallet et al. 2019). Large scale snow thickness and snow structural information across Svalbard are needed to better understand the spatial distribution of snow accumulation and its interannual variability. In addition, such measurements provide a snapshot into spatial patterns of seasonal precipitation that are otherwise barely covered by the operational precipitation gauges. Surveys by ground penetrating

radar (GPR) are accurate and cost-efficient, and have been conducted in Svalbard for more than 25 years, thus permitting assessment of long-term changes. These data complement the single-point snow monitoring measurements and seasonal measurement campaigns on glaciers and tundra. The campaigns so far have focused on particular areas, so the data are sparse. The purpose of this report is to compile information about the conducted GPR snow cover measurements and to define standards for measurements and data sharing. The activities initiated in this project will be continued in the coming years and extended with a comprehensive data analysis.

2. Fundamentals of radar surveying of snow cover

2.1. Principles of radio-echo sounding

The radio-echo sounding (RES) method uses induced electromagnetic radiation in the wavelength spectrum from 100 m to 100 mm. The survey consists of transmitting an electromagnetic pulse of a certain frequency to the ground (snow in our case), receiving the reflected signal, and recording the return time and amplitude of the signal.

The propagation of electromagnetic waves is determined by the characteristics of the electromagnetic spectrum and electromagnetic properties of the surveyed material defined by its permittivity, permeability, and conductivity. In environmental radar research, it is assumed that the probing is applied to non-conductive and non-magnetic materials (dielectrics).

The sounding depth range depends on many factors, including several processes of loss of transmitted electromagnetic energy, the most important being geometric spreading, scattering,

and attenuation. Due to geometric spreading, the power of the radar signal decreases with the square of the distance to the transmitter, while it decreases exponentially with depth due to attenuation. When probing cryospheric systems, intense energy attenuation can occur in water-saturated sediments or sediments containing salt solutions. Energy passing through is also subject to scattering or refraction on the structures and objects present in the surveyed material depending on the sounding wavelength and the size of these objects (Plewes and Hubbard 2001, Neal 2004). The reflection of the radar wave at the boundaries of materials with different dielectric properties is the basis for recognising the internal structure. Such dielectric contrasts are usually found at the bottom of the winter snow cover (interface snow-ground or snow-ice), thus making the technique well suited for mapping the vertical extent of the snowpack. The reflection coefficient (R) is derived from the dielectric contrast of the adjacent layers and ranges between -1 and 1. The probability of properly identifying the boundary between structures increases with the rise of the absolute value of the reflection coefficient.

2.2. Dielectric properties of the snowpack

The dielectric properties of snow (Table 1) are mainly determined by the mutual contribution of the three basic components that build the snow cover, i.e., ice, air, and water. Their individual dielectric properties are significantly different; hence their contribution to the snow cover substantially impacts the course and results of radio-echo sounding. Changing the proportion of the components also changes the dielectric properties of the entire snow cover. The increase in the gaseous fraction (air) translates into an increased radar wave velocity (RWV) in the snow cover, while the increase of the solid fraction (ice), and even more of the liquid fraction (water) decrease the RWV in the snow cover. The RWV is inversely dependent on the square root of the relative permittivity. Spatial and temporal variation

in snow cover dielectric characteristics should be considered in the time-to-depth conversion process.

The contrast of the dielectric properties of adjacent materials affects the possibility of their distinction. Table 1 shows a significant discrepancy between the permittivity of dry snow and most of the typical materials that make up the snow cover base. The absolute value of the reflection coefficient is in the range of 0.06 – 0.61 (Grabiec 2017), which indicates a high probability of the recognition of the boundary between the dry snowpack and the base, regardless of its type. When the snowpack contains a significant proportion of water, the contrast with some types of beddings (glacier ice, firn, sea ice, lake ice, basal ice) becomes blurred, making separating these structures difficult.

Table 1: Dielectric characteristics of snowpack components, snowpack of different properties, and formations of snowpack bedding (based on Davis and Annan 1989; Neal 2004; Baker et al. 2007; Grabiec et al. 2011; Grabiec 2017)

Material	Relative permittivity (dielectric constant) (ϵ_r)	Radar wave velocity (RWV) [$m\ ns^{-1}$]
SNOWPACK COMPONENTS		
Ice	3.2	0.168
Air	1	0.30
Freshwater	80	0.03
SNOWPACK		
Fresh snow (200 $kg\ m^{-3}$, w=0%)	1.36	0.26
Dry snow (350 $kg\ m^{-3}$, w=0%)	1.65	0.23
Dry snow (500 $kg\ m^{-3}$, w=0%)	2	0.21
Wet snow (500 $kg\ m^{-3}$, w=5%)	2.82	0.18
Water-saturated snow (500 $kg\ m^{-3}$, w=10%)	3.83	0.15
Slush (500 $kg\ m^{-3}$, w=15%)	5.06	0.13
SNOWPACK BASE (selected materials)		
Glacier ice	3-4	0.15-0.17
Firn	2.5	0.19
Dry till (moraine)	7.4-21.1	0.10-0.12
Saturated till (moraine)	24-34	0.10-0.12
Bedrock	4-9	0.10-0.13

Due to the heterogeneous nature of snow and, consequently, different dielectric properties of individual snow layers, RES seems to be an effective tool for identifying the internal structure of snow cover (Harper and Bradford 2003; Yamamoto et al. 2004; Marshall et al. 2007; Heilig et al. 2009). Hard layers, e.g. ice lenses, ice crusts, and ice layers, are particularly helpful in delimiting boundary layers in snow cover (Marshall et al. 2007; Yamamoto et al. 2004; Dunse et al. 2008). The distinction of snow layers based on the difference in their reflectivity requires that the density contrast between the layers be higher than 100 kg m^{-3} (Yamamoto et al. 2004).

The above considerations regarding the possibility of recognising the snow cover's depth and internal structure should also take into account the technical conditions of the radar survey, such as the sounding radar wave frequency, trace-to-trace interval, sampling frequency, etc.

2.3. Snow radio-echo sounders

Commercial impulse radars, referred to as ground penetrating radars (GPR), are commonly used in snow cover soundings. These devices are characterised by a simple, modular structure, intuitive operation and setting of measurement parameters, the possibility of visualising the results in real time, a data collection system, integration with positioning systems (GNSS receivers), and distance measurement devices (odometers). GPR in snow cover surveys applies high-frequency antennas (commonly, 450 MHz – 2.4 GHz), ensuring a sufficient penetration depth with high vertical resolution. GPR systems were used to obtain the majority of data presented in this report.

Frequency Modulated Continuous Wave (FMCW) radars are also applied in snow cover studies. The principle of FMCW radar is based on the difference in the radar wave frequency transmitted and reflected from the object. FMCW radar is characterised by operation in a high-frequency range (above 1 GHz). Therefore, it allows obtaining results with the high vertical resolution required for analyses of the snow cover structure (e.g. Marshall et al. 2007) or identification of glacier facies (Langley et al. 2008).

2.4. Advantages and limitations of radar sounding of snow

The method has several advantages. Due to the non-invasive nature of sounding, GPRs are a desirable method in areas where environmental protection regulations limit field surveys that interfere with the ground (national parks, nature reserves, and other forms of protection). Due to its mobility and quick measurement times, this method is less time-consuming and cost-intensive than the classic methods of manual snow cover probing. It allows for immediate recognition of the two-dimensional image of the surface layer of the ground (snow cover).

Due to snow cover properties (dry snow cover is highly 'transparent' to radar waves), the depth of snow probing is not a critical limitation. With appropriate measurement parameters and equipment selection, it is possible to recognise snow structures, even of extreme depth.

Like any geophysical method, RES also provides indirect information about the varying geophysical properties of the ground. In the case of GPR, the recorded variable is the two-way travel time of the signal transmitted from the radar and reflected from the dielectric discontinuities. A main RES analysis challenge is obtaining reliable calibration and validation data allowing for the time-to-depth conversion. For this purpose, it is common practice to perform control field measurements to determine the actual depth and snow cover structure (snow cores, snow pits). The use of velocity profiling (common mid-point) is more time-consuming and costly compared with classic field methods of snow depth and structure measurement.

An important factor determining the quality of the measurement results is the vertical resolution of the radar sounding, which depends on the centre frequency of the antenna and the dielectric properties of the snow cover. Assuming that most measurements are made in dry snow with an average density of 350 kg m^{-3} , using antennas with a centre frequency between 450 MHz and 2.4 GHz, the vertical resolution calculated as $\lambda/4$ may range

from 0.11 m to 0.04 m. As a result, the accuracy of separating the boundaries and the snow depth and the possibility of distinguishing thin layers remains limited.

Interpretation issues of the GPR image remain challenging. Independent information from snow pit investigations, shallow cores or manual snow probing ease interpretation of GPR data and identification of the internal reflection horizon

originating from the last summer surface. The identification of the bottom of the snow cover may pose particular difficulties in areas with similar dielectric properties of the underlying material, e.g. in the firn zone. Despite the attempts made (e.g. Mitterer et al. 2011; Grabiec et al. 2020), a link between the properties of the radar reflection and the physical properties of the snow cover remains a challenge.

3. Survey design and data processing

3.1. Survey design

Defining the purpose of the research: the methodology discussed in this chapter is dedicated to shallow soundings aimed at determining the depth and distribution of seasonal snow cover, deposited mainly on glaciers and in their immediate vicinity. It cannot be considered universal for all types of GPR sounding conducted in polar regions. The precise definition of the purpose and the object being studied should always be the starting point for the correct planning of the survey.

Defining the layout of the radar profiles and their mutual relations: the recorded data consist of continuous points arranged in profiles with defined start and end points. In order to obtain a full view of the snow cover distribution, a grid of longitudinal and transverse profiles (or zig-zag) should be designed after defining the object, area and purpose. This can be problematic in highly crevassed areas (e.g. frontal parts of tidewater glaciers and surging glaciers), snow deposited on unstable sea ice and terrain with a slope angle exceeding 15 degrees. In areas with diversified ground relief, it is recommended to increase the density of the radar profile grid. For example, the profile density on the frequently monitored glaciers on southern Spitsbergen is c. 2000 m of GPR profile per km² on Werenskioldbreen and 1650 m of GPR profile per km² on Hansbreen (Laska et al. 2017).

Antenna selection: according to the assumed

sounding depth, the dimensions of the investigated object and the expected vertical resolution, and the appropriate antenna type and frequency should be selected. In the case of determining the depth of the seasonal snow cover, the key reflection horizons are: in the ablation zone of glacier, the glacier ice surface; in the accumulation zone of glaciers, the top of the firn layer; on the tundra, the ground surface. In relation with the applications on glaciers, shielded antennas with a frequency of about 800 MHz are most common. They allow coverage of a depth range of at least 10 – 20 m, depending on physical properties of the snow and limited by the user-specified time window. For more detailed results, it is recommended to use higher frequency antennas, such as 1.6 GHz. They are especially recommended for sounding snow with a low depth, e.g. on the tundra or lakes. The first measurements using such frequencies were carried out in Svalbard in recent years. However, the results are not published yet. The theoretical vertical measurement resolution is $\frac{1}{4}$ of the wavelength emitted by the antenna (Hubbard and Glasser 2005; Berthling and Melvold 2008). For example, for an antenna with a frequency of 800 MHz, it has been calculated as 0.066 m.

Construction of the platform for transporting the radar set: depending on the configuration, the complete radar set will consist of a control unit connected to two (or more) individual dipole antennas – transmitting, Tx and receiving, Rx (for unshielded antennas), or Tx-Rx antennas enclosed

Figure 1: Example of the GPR system configuration: A - snowmobile with navigator, B - sled with GPR operator, C - pulkas with antenna(s) in a waterproof cover (Photo: Mariusz Grabiec).

in a common housing (for shielded antennas). Shielding makes it possible to separate random, external signals emitted by other neighbouring electronic devices. In both cases, the connection is mainly via optical fibres, which allow fast and undisturbed data streaming. Some designs enable simultaneous sounding with two or more antennas of different frequencies. In addition, the control unit is connected to a portable field computer (or tablet), resistant to moisture, shock, and low temperature, with a battery of sufficiently large capacity. To increase the positioning accuracy, an additional connection to an external GNSS receiver is advised. The entire configuration is shown in Figure 1. Depending on the extent of the area of interest, this set can be transported manually by operator(s), pulled on pulkas, tracked by a snowmobile or installed under a helicopter. There are also designs that can be integrated with unmanned aerial vehicles, UAVs (e.g. Vergnano et al. 2022).

Positioning and measuring the distance: for simple, general surveys, using a laptop built-in or USB standalone GNSS receiver may be sufficient (XY accuracy approx. ± 5 m, Z accuracy approx. 10 m). However, if the objective is focused on a detailed

analysis (e.g. determination of the snow cover vertical gradients, glacier surface hypsometry, terrain relief, etc.), a parallel connection with the GNSS receiver is advised. Its sampling interval should be the same as the GPR trace-to-trace time interval. Using differential kinematic mode (dGPS) and a fixed reference station enables XYZ accuracy to be obtained at ± 0.1 m. However, this requires additional effort – appropriate post-processing and data synchronisation (described in the section 3.4 ‘Data processing’). There are various methods of measuring the distance (GNSS receiver, wheel or hip-chain odometers and others) during the GPR survey. Due to the specificity of the research area, common surveys are based on GNSS positioning.

3.2. Measurements settings

Triggering method: there are three ways of triggering the radar signal: manual (practical for single measurements, e.g. RWV measurements by the common midpoint method), distance (using external odometers) and time (used most often in polar surveys). Due to the large diversity of the surface relief, it is recommended to set regular and fast sampling. Most researchers in Svalbard use one in the range 0.2-0.3 s. The most popular setting is

0.2 s (Appendix 1). While maintaining a constant measurement speed of c. 20 km/h, this setting results in a distance of c. 1.0–1.5 m between successive traces.

Time window: it defines the maximum time range of the radar wave recorded for each trace in the investigated substrate. The time window should be set to allow for the arrival of the return signal from the deepest interfaces of interest. This value is usually expressed in nanoseconds, which, with a defined RWV, allows for the determination of the depth. When estimating this parameter, a 30% allowance for error should be applied (Grabiec 2017, after Sensors & Software 1992-1999). For the glaciers of southern Spitsbergen, the time window mostly used is 80 ns (and normally between 45 and 172 ns) when using an 800 MHz antenna. Such a setting makes it possible to fully sample the snow cover, as it implies a penetration depth of c. 7.0–8.4 m.

Sampling frequency: this parameter indicates how often a given trace is sampled. For a given time window, setting the sampling frequency determines how many points will be recorded per trace. Commercial GPR systems generate signals with a frequency in the range of 0.5-1.5 f , where f is the value of the centre frequency (Grabiec 2017). In order to maximise the vertical resolution of the measurement, it is recommended to set the sampling frequency not lower than six times the centre frequency of the antenna being used (Berthling and Melvold 2008).

Number of samples: a single trace consists of a predefined number of samples. They represent digitally the value of the wave amplitude per time unit. The higher the value, the higher the theoretical amplitude resolution. When using 800 MHz antennas, this parameter is most often set to 1024.

3.3. GPR surveying

Depending on the extent of the area of interest, the implementation of the entire survey plan may take up to several hours, which means that it is necessary

to properly prepare for it, and fieldwork should be carried out in favourable weather conditions. This is crucial particularly when working in high-risk areas (such as crevassed areas or slopes prone to avalanches). Responsibilities should be divided between at least two people: the equipment operator, who handles the electronics and is focused on its correct operation, and the guide, who leads the team, following the track prepared in advance and trying to maintain a constant speed. In the case of work based on snowmobiles, a reasonable speed is around 20–30 km/h. However, this speed should be much lower in the case of driving on rough terrain or over sastrugi. In difficult terrain such as crevasse fields, it may be necessary to reevaluate and adjust the planned survey profiles. Because both the control unit and the antenna electronics are powered with replaceable battery packs, it is recommended to heat spare batteries with body heat. During their replacement, the operator should check that connection plugs are dry and free of snow or ice. Successive profiles should be finished with a noticeable change of the heading. It is recommended to divide long profiles if their length exceeds 5–7.5 km (around 1000 seconds).

3.4. Data processing

Data processing should start with checking the consistency and integrity of the collected data. At the next stage, it is worth defining the course and orientation of the profiles. Applying GIS software for the initial visualisation of profiles' locations could be helpful here. It is also a particularly useful tool for referencing the results of manual point measurements which are used to calibrate the GPR data. When working with GPR profiles, it is recommended to reduce the time window presented on the vertical axis to the range of the analysed reflection horizon. In the next step, the recorded profiles should be cross-checked to remove unnecessary or damaged sections. Those may occur e.g. as a result of antenna rotation during the measurement, weak or drained battery of the antenna electronics, and unplanned stops during data recording. For later analysis, it may be necessary to synchronise the data from the GPR

with the data from the GNSS receiver. This can be done by combining data columns from both independent measurements using the recording time. Some dedicated GPR software packages are able to perform this procedure in a fully automatic way.

There is no single, obligatory set of rules for snow data processing. It is assumed that post-processing of GPR data aims to increase the signal-to-noise ratio, thereby facilitating interpretation of radargrams. When using filters, referring to the applicable instructions for the software being used may be helpful (e.g. ReflexW 3D, RadExplorer, etc.). The mandatory filters include: Time-Zero correction, which allows removing the delay time of first arrivals (direct wave) (especially important when the antenna is located above the investigated surface) and Direct-Current removal (DC removal). In areas with slope exceeding 6° , it is recommended to use Topographic correction (Lehmann and Green 2000). Other filters, such as Dewow, Gain, Background removal or Bandpass filtering, should be used moderately as their overuse may cause misinterpretations and increase measurement errors.

3.5. Validation

Manual point measurements: since GPR is an indirect method, the reliability of the measurements depends on the direct, *in-situ* measurements. For this purpose, an avalanche probe can be used to determine the seasonal snow thickness. The reliability of validation soundings with the use of an avalanche probe is limited in the case of thick internal ice layers. This method, however, has its limitations in the glacier accumulation zone, where it is possible to penetrate into the firn. Validation can also be performed quickly using shallow snow cores collected with a coring system, e.g. Kovacs Mark III. However, it is not trivial to

determine the accurate thickness due to strong warming events in Svalbard. A coring system, apart from the snow depth, provides information on the bulk density of the seasonal snow cover, which may contribute to a better estimate of the RWV within the analysed material, and allow construction of a calibration curve between snow-water equivalents (SWE) and RWV, which in turn allows mapping of the SWE over large surface areas for modelling and remote sensing purposes. In addition, an experienced person can detect the snow-firn interface. Full and detailed information about the snowpack stratigraphy, its thickness and density, as well as the snow-firn interface is more precisely determined using traditional snowpit work. However, that procedure requires a lot of effort and time. Regardless of the chosen direct method, point measurements should be made in the immediate vicinity of the GPR profile, at least in several places representing different glacier zones, or evenly distributed over the tundra surface, ultimately capturing the natural variability (thin, thick, soft, and hard snowpacks) so to cover the range of RWV.

3.6. Quality of the data series

A proper identification of the internal reflection horizon originating from the last summer surface on the radar profiles and its accuracy can be estimated by using the standard deviation of a multiple (e.g. five) repetitions of the analysis of the main profile, representing the entire altitude range of the analysed area. For glacial areas, it is worth verifying such a value separately for the ablation and accumulation zones. The correct determination of the appropriate horizon above the equilibrium line may be difficult to perform and only possible through validation with manual point measurements (Laska et al. 2017). Therefore, the largest deviation occurs close to the equilibrium-line altitude (Figure 2).

3.7. Data export formats

Registered data formats and the number of files related to a single profile vary depending on the equipment and software used. Therefore, in the context of exporting the data, it is recommended to focus on the universal data formats, e.g. text file (.csv) with the following columns: X and Y coordinates, trace number, and two-way travel time (TWTT) and depth. Having the TWTT information recorded allows the exported data to be reanalysed if there is a need to modify the RWV. Datasets prepared in this way can be used successfully as input to the GIS software or software/programming language for scientific computing to facilitate the interpretation of the obtained results and their appropriate visualisation.

Figure 2: Standard deviation of the identification of the snow base from GPR profiles in the central line of Hansbreen (modified after Grabiec 2017).

4. Overview of radar sounding applications in snow surveys in Svalbard

Snow distribution in high-latitude landscapes plays a key role in defining energy and moisture relationships associated with the Earth's climate system (Melvold 2008). The GPR method has been used in snow measurements for more than four decades. The first snow surveys in Svalbard using GPR date back to the beginning of the 1990s. However, only during the last decade has regular monitoring been carried out in Svalbard using GPR.

GPR is used both for monitoring snow cover on glaciers and on the tundra. Measurements take the form of profiles ranging from a few kilometres to several hundred kilometres long or measurements on a predefined measurement grid (Figure 3). The

first measurements were made at the Endalselva catchment in the vicinity of Longyearbyen as well as in De Geerdalen in 1991-1994 (Tveit and Killingtveit, 1994). In De Geerdalen, the measurements were repeated in 2001 (Vonk 2001 after Winther et al. 2003). For the Ny-Ålesund area, the first published results were collected in May 1996 at Kongsvegen (Kohler et al. 2003) and in May 1998 in the lower Bayelva catchment. The measurements in the lower Bayelva catchment were done in the grid and covered an area of 2 x 1.5 km (Bruland et al. 2001; Sand et al. 2001). These measurements were repeated in 2000 (Winther et al. 2003). The first glacial measurements were published by Winther et al. (1998) and Kohler et al.

Figure 3: Location of ground penetrating radar measurements of snow cover in Svalbard in 1996-2022. 1- Nannbreen, 2 – Werenskioldbreen, 3 – Hansbreen, 4 – Amundsenisen, 5 – Storbreen and 6 – Flatbreen. Metadata and GPS data (.shp) tracks are available from Ignatiuk et al. (2022).

(2003). These included longitudinal and transverse transects on Slakbreen in 1997, and Kongsvegen in 1996, respectively. Comprehensive GPR surveys were performed between 1997 and 1999 at thirteen sites in Svalbard. Measurements were made

on both the tundra and glaciers in the form of four west to east transects (Sand et al. 2003). In 2012, 2014, and 2016-2017, regular measurements were made at Lomonosovfonna (Van Pelt et al. 2014) and in 2013-2015 at Werenskioldbreen (Appendix

1). Currently, the longest observation series are conducted and continued on Austfonna (1999, 2004-2018) (Pinglot et al. 2001; Taurisano et al. 2007; Dunse et al. 2009), which alone accounts for more than 25% of all GPR data from Svalbard, and Hansbeen (2008, 2011, 2013-2019, 2022) (Grabiec et al. 2010; Laska et al. 2017). Snow cover monitoring on Foxfonna close to Longyearbyen (UNIS, personal communication from A. Hodson) is also regularly carried out. At Austre Grønfjordbreen, close to Barentsburg, GPR snow cover observations have been carried out since 2013 (Sosnovsky et al. 2015; Lavrentiev et al. 2018; Singh et al. 2020; Elagina et al. 2021). Occasional campaigns include Amundsenisen (2001, 2006, 2013) (Melvold 2008; Grabiec et al. 2011; Laska et al. 2017), Flatbreen and Storbreen (2013, 2014, 2015 and 2018) (Laska et al. 2017; Barzycka et al. 2020). In the non-glaciated tundra areas, observations are currently carried out in Hornsund (Fuglebekken and Revdalen) (Kępski 2021), Adventdalen close to Longyearbyen (NORCE) and Brøggerhalvøya close to Ny-Ålesund (NPI).

Most of the measurements were made with Malå RAMAC/ProEx survey systems, although at the beginning of the measurements, in the early 1990s, PulseEKKO and GSSI SIR 2 (Appendix 1) systems were sometimes used. Shielded antennas were used for most of the measurements. The 800 MHz antenna has become a standard in the last two decades. Nevertheless, in the 1990s measurements were also made with antennas with a 450-500 MHz centre frequency. In recent years, the first attempts to use high-frequency antennas (e.g. 1.6 GHz) were carried out for more detailed measurements of snowpack stratigraphy. Most measurements were made using GNSS RTK positioning mode. The most popular method of data validation in regards to snow thickness or SWE validation are snowpits and shallow coring. Where there is a permanent network of snow accumulation and ablation stakes (Hansbreen, Werenskioldbreen, Fuglebekken), they are used for data validation.

The GPR snow measurements are a common method for studying large-scale patterns of snow distribution and the gradient of snow accumulation

across glaciers in Svalbard (Winther et al. 1998, 2003, Melvold 2008; Bruland et al. 2001; Pinglot et al. 2001; Pälli et al. 2002; Sand et al. 2003; Taurisano et al. 2007; Grabiec et al. 2011; Laska et al. 2017). Observations of the spatial variability of snow cover on glaciers (Figure 4) allow us to determine the seasonal variability of snow cover and to study the factors influencing snow redistribution. Many authors (e.g. Taurisano et al. 2007; Laska et al. 2017) indicate that, despite the annual variability of the snow thickness, its distribution showed the same pattern in different years. Factors contributing to the spatial distribution of snow cover can also be determined for specific glaciers. For example, for Hansbreen, an increase in snow depth towards the north on the western tributary glaciers, and higher snow accumulation in the western part of Hansbreen were found (Figure 5). This suggests that snow distribution is dominated by wind-blown redistribution rather than spatial precipitation variability (Grabiec et al. 2011; Laska et al. 2017). In the case of Austfonna (Figure 6), which has a simple dome shape, the snow distribution is largely controlled both by the distribution of precipitation and the redistribution of snow by wind drift (Pinglot et al. 2001; Taurisano et al. 2007). The analyses carried out based on GPR research show different spatial accumulation gradients for the entire Svalbard region. Winther et al. (1998), based on measurements in the central and northern parts of Svalbard, suggest a gradient of snow accumulation from the west coast towards the east. This pattern was not observed in the Hornsund area (Laska et al. 2017).

The data from shallow GPR surveys (shallow means mainly aimed at snow studies) can be exploited for information about the multi-year sequence of glacier-facies distribution, which provides information for validation of the surface mass balance data (Dunse et al. 2009; Uszczyk et al. 2019; Barzycka et al. 2020). Based on the characteristic signal-reflection pattern dependent on the typical occurrence and strength of dielectric contrasts that occur for different facies on the glacier, it may be possible to identify firn, superimposed ice (SI), and glacial ice zones (Dunse et al. 2009). Usually, in such analyses the upper

Figure 4: Spatial distribution of the snow cover on Hansbreen, Werenskioldbreen and Nannbreen (modified after Laska et al. 2017).

layer of every profile (corresponding to the snow cover) is excluded from the interpretation and the firn, superimposed ice and ice interface are determined manually in every GPR profile (Barzycka et al. 2020). Validation of the results is based on

the comparison between GPR results and SAR images (Dunse et al. 2009; Barzycka et al. 2020). Spatial analysis of glacier facies allows the study of changes of the surface of glaciers caused by a changing climate, as well as distinguishing changes in the mass balance in the southern and northern parts of Svalbard. Observations on Austfonna in the years 2003-2006 show an increase of the extent of the firn zone at the expense of the superimposed ice extent (Figure 7), in contrast with Hansbreen, where the superimposed ice zone disappeared and the extent of the firn zone decreased by 44.5% over 2007-2017 (Figure 8).

Snow depth data from GPR measurements, as well as snow pits, provide important data for calibration and/or validation of models simulating glacier climatic mass balance, snow conditions and runoff (e.g. Schuler et al. 2007; Aas et al. 2016; Østby et al. 2017; Van Pelt et al. 2019, 2021; Schuler and Østby 2020). Observed snow depth in spring can be combined with snow pit (bulk) density to give winter balance estimates. Where snow probing gives local (point) snow depth estimates, GPR has the advantage that it can be used to estimate the spatial average of snow thickness. This is relevant for the validation and calibration of models that

Figure 5: GPR-derived snow depth as a function of elevation on Hansbreen in April 2008, measured along specific parallel profiles: eastern, central and western in the elevation range 200–350 m a.s.l. (modified after Grabiec et al. 2011).

Figure 6: Snow depth profiles along the south-west-north-east transects on Austfonna (modified after Pinglot et al. 2001, Taurisano et al. 2007, and Dunse et al. 2009).

generate gridded (i.e. grid-cell averaged) results. In addition, the data collected by GNSS receivers during GPR measurements are used e.g. for quality assessment of digital elevation models (DEM) derived from space-borne and aerial images

(Błaszczuk et al. 2019). It is also possible to use the data to locate crevasses on glaciers, which can be used to improve the safety of fieldwork on glaciers or to monitor changes in glacier dynamics (e.g. Dunse et al. 2015).

Figure 7: (a) GPR-derived glacier facies across Austfonna, end of summer 2006, distinguishing between firm (F1, F2 and F3), superimposed ice (SI) and glacier ice (GI). The background image shows average SAR backscatter intensity during the winters of 2005 to 2007. (b) Example of the characteristics of GPR signatures from different glacier facies along a 30-km long transect from the summit of Austfonna to the ablation area of Etonbreen. The solid green line indicates the last summer surface 2006 (modified after Dunse et al. 2009).

Figure 8: Results of GPR visual interpretation and SAR classification on Hansbreen summer surface in 2010 and 2017. ICE-glacier ice, SI-superimposed ice. Background Landsat 7 and 8 images courtesy of the U.S. Geological Survey, Sentinel-2 images courtesy of the European Space Agency (modified after Barzycka et al. 2020).

5. Contributions to interdisciplinarity

The importance of Svalbard snow cover research, its interdisciplinary potential and its impact on terrestrial, glacier and sea ice research have been widely discussed in SESS reports for snow research (Gallet et al. 2019; Malnes et al. 2021; Killie et al. 2021; Salzano et al. 2021a, 2021b) as well as permafrost monitoring studies (Christiansen et al. 2019, 2020) and Svalbard hydrology (Nowak et al. 2021). Snow cover measurements using GPR, in particular their potential to aid understanding of the spatial distribution of snow, are fundamental for Svalbard ecosystem studies. For example, rain on snow events are currently observed widely in the high Arctic, and particularly in Svalbard. Even if it is very challenging to determine the amount of internal ice within the snowpack or the amount of basal ice (at the ground–snow interface), radar measurements can provide a broad overview of the extent of icing during winter. Thus, large areas where vegetation and ungulates are living can be explored and a better link between climate warming and ecosystem can be made, as well as offering a new strategy to further improve our monitoring

and research strategies. Moreover, interest in the type, amount, and activities of the microbial community is growing. Algae and bacteria need nutrients and acceptable temperature to survive: thus, determining the amount of icing (i.e. warming) within the snowpack and the firn is also of interest for microbiological research. Paleoclimate studies are also increasingly focused on the use of radar data for two reasons: first, to find the most appropriate site for drilling ice cores, especially to find a location where the ice is not disturbed so the dating is easy and precise; second, observations of icing inside the snow or the disappearance of firn would show that a site may have been strongly affected by warming in previous years, thus rendering the dating very complex because the signal – often recorded using oxygen isotopes – is flattened (no more seasonality) or even obliterated. Radar measurements are now widely used and provide not only pure glaciological information, but also support data for other disciplines as well as defining the optimal site for a specific research purpose.

6. Unanswered questions/Future challenges

Several challenges must be faced related to the use of GPR in snow research. One of the most important is the use of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV) for GPR snow cover measurements. Both multi-rotor

and fixed-wing drones outfitted with GPR can open up new research horizons. The first tests in the Italian Alps (Vergnano et al. 2022), Quebec (Valence et al. 2022), and Svalbard (carried out by NORCE

(Jenssen and Jacobsen 2021)) show promising results. By performing GPR measurements from UAVs, it will be possible to study snow cover over strongly crevassed glacier areas and on steep mountain slopes. Indeed, many Svalbard glaciers are small and some of their accumulation areas are in basins (or bowls, lobes) with steep terrain. Due to increased melting over summer, areas which were safe in the past are now becoming more hazardous. Old crevasses in these bowls used to be snow filled during springtime, but can now simply be covered by a thin snow bridge, making them dangerous to cross. Measurements in these areas are important to understand water balance and glacier mass balance, and are becoming even more important now that they are sometimes the only part of the glacier where snow remains in summer. In the past, we could interpolate the amount of snow on these parts of the glacier from data collected at lower altitude. Today the inaccessibility of these areas for surface-based measurements and the resulting lack of information increases our uncertainty on snow cover depth and duration. The use of UAVs will allow us to cover these and larger areas of the terrain, making the dataset more representative.

Another challenge is to broaden the areas where measurements have been done so far, to better define the spatial and temporal variability of Svalbard's snow cover. This will allow us to track changes that take place in the cryosphere under a dynamically changing climate. Data with better spatial coverage will also contribute to better validation and calibration of remote sensing products and climate models. It is known that Svalbard has strong north-south and east-west gradients in terms of snow cover, and a glance at a map shows that it is in central Spitsbergen, where precipitation is lowest, that we observe the least glaciation. Changing climate will change the amount of precipitation, in absolute values, with most of it coming in the form of rain and during summer or autumn, enhancing the melt of the glaciers even further. The change of precipitation patterns will strongly affect glacier mass balance and the current link between climate and mass balance may in the future follow different regimes even at the scale of Svalbard if on top of summer

melting, autumn melting and/or winter rain events become more frequent. To better understand the long-term variability of snow cover distribution and its future changes, it is thus necessary to conduct regular monitoring using GPR in representative areas of Svalbard, selected to cover most of the precipitation gradient. Monitoring of larger glaciers at higher altitude would also be welcome. These glaciers are still relatively safe to travel on, and thus may not yet require use of UAV-mounted GPR. However, they are also melting, and this is where changes in terms of snow amount and type (dry, wet or icy) will be easiest to detect in a near future. While it is important to continue studying the small glaciers, as this is where we have most of our longer time series, those glacier are sadly destined to disappear in the coming decades. The possibility remains that the larger ones will retreat but adapt to climate change and survive, unless temperatures continue to rise to the point where they will no longer allow any glacier in Svalbard to accumulate ice.

Shallow snowpacks in a tundra environment and on mountain slopes pose another challenge. Relatively popular 500-800 MHz antennas used for snow mapping over the glaciers do not give satisfactory results in shallow (below 50 cm) snow and in areas covered by basal ice. Higher-frequency antennas (over 1.2 GHz) with smaller near-field effects can overcome the problems on the tundra. Their greater vertical resolution allows successful detection, e.g. even 16 cm thin snowpack in the case of the 1.6 GHz antenna. However, it should be noted that in the case of fresh snow, the sledges/pulkas carrying the GPR can significantly compact the surface, causing underestimation of original snow depth (McGrath et al. 2019), which imposes a limitation to the use of GPR in zones with low snow accumulation. One way to address that issue would be to build a very light radar sledge which is attached to the side of a snowmobile, thus measuring over an undisturbed snow surface and limiting the physical impact on it. Nevertheless, higher-frequency antennas can provide insight into snow stratigraphy and be used e.g. for avalanche prediction, and to measure the amount of internal or basal ice. Especially interesting results on shallow

snow may be given by upward-looking ground penetrating radars (upGPR) installed at fixed positions, providing continuous data (Heilig et al. 2009; Mitterer et al. 2011; Schmid et al. 2014; Schmid et al. 2015). These types of studies have not been carried out so far in Svalbard but may provide valuable supplementary data to study the continuous evolution of snow cover at selected specific sites.

Most of the GPR data collected so far is not currently available in any open-access data repository. A comprehensive collection of the studies on which this report is based, and recommendations for metadata and data quality should be the first step to making GPR data more accessible. In the interest of the research community, there should be a will to construct an open-access international database for snow GPR-based data similar to the Glacier Thickness Database (GlaThiDa) hosted by the World Glacier Monitoring Service (WGMS)

7. Recommendations for future

Measurements of snow cover depth using GPR differ depending on whether the measurements are performed on a glacier or on the tundra, as well as on the predicted depth of the snow cover and the purpose of the study. Nevertheless, it is possible to extract some general recommendations regarding fieldwork and data processing and formatting for data exchange, which we have grouped below into appropriate subsections. These are followed by some recommendations for future work under subsection “New Challenges”.

Survey:

- Repeated measurements in successive years should be made on the same GNSS tracks whenever safety conditions allow.
- In order to validate the results, it is recommended to perform snow measurements (snow depth, snow pit-stratigraphy, snow water equivalent (SWE)) or shallow coring (snow depth, SWE). It is not recommended to use snow probes or measurements from ablation stakes, as this may result in larger errors.
- The frequency of antennas used for snow cover measurements should not be less than 750 MHz. In the case of surveys of shallow snowpack (tundra environment, mountain slopes) it is recommended to use higher-frequency antennas (above 1 GHz).

Processing:

- For greater accuracy when determining the

depth of snow cover, it is recommended use the standard deviation of multiple (e.g. five) repetitions of the analysis of the main GPR profile, representing the entire altitude range of the analysed area.

- The basic processing of the data should include as mandatory steps Time-Zero correction and DC removal filters.
- The RWV used in the data processing and time-to-depth conversion should be derived from the point validation measurements of snow depth (from snow pit or coring) and the corresponding record of the TWTT to the snow base.

Data sharing:

- The shared GPR data should have a full metadata description as proposed in this report (link to data repository). The processed data structure for snow depth should contain a minimum as follows: X and Y coordinates, trace number, TWTT to the snow base and snow depth.

New challenges:

- Adaptation of UAVs to perform autonomous GPR measurements of the snow cover.
- The programmed conducted in the late 1990s for recognition of regional variations in snow accumulation in W–E and N–S transects (Sand et al. 2003) should be repeated for all of Svalbard in order to determine changes in the accumulation of snow cover under ongoing climate change.

- To promote gender balance, the snow GPR research community should encourage women

to participate in the GPR campaigns and studies.

8. Data availability

Due to the large number of partners and available

data, information is provided in Appendix 2.

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Appendix 1

Snow cover measurements made using ground-penetrating radar (GPR) from 1997 to 2022 on the basis of collected and published data. A detailed table with metadata can be found in Ignatiuk et al. 2022.

Survey area and coordinates	Date of the survey (YYYY-MM-DD) and total distance [km]	Time window [ns]	Trace-to-trace time interval [s]	Average trace-to-trace distance interval [m]	Snow depth validation method (Positioning mode)	Snow RWV applied [m, ns]
Amundsenisen ³⁾	200104XX [20.4]	179	0.2	0.8	snow probe, snow pit (RTK GNSS)	
Amundsenisen ²⁾	20060421-27 [44.5]	405		1	(wheel odometer)	0.21
Amundsenisen ¹⁾	20130505 [56.7]	80	0.2	1.0-1.5	snow pit (RTK GNSS)	0.21
Amundsenisen- Högstebreen ¹⁾	20110416 [66]	98.9	0.2	1.31	GNSS	
Ariebreen ¹⁾	2014		0.2	1.0-1.5	snow pit (RTK GNSS)	0.21
Austfonna ³⁾	1999 [235]	105			snow pit, core	
Austfonna ¹⁾	2004 [197] 2005 [140] 2006 [143] 2007 [187] 2008 [109] 2009 [138] 2010 [98] 2011 [291] 2012 [346] 2013 [299] 2014 [191] 2015 [69] 2016 [61] 2017 [219] 2018 [114]	126 (2004-2006, 2008-2009) 145 (2007) 130 (2010) 128 (2011-2012) 139 (2013) 145 (2014) 172 (2015-2018)	0.5 (2004-2005). 0.05 (2006-2007). 0.05, 0.01 (2008-2015)	2 (2004-2005). 0.25 (2006-2007). 0.25, 0.5 (2008-2018)	snow pit, core	
Austfonna ¹⁾	2006	126	0.05	0.25	snow pit, core	
Austre Grønfyordbreen ⁶⁾	2014					
Brøggerhalvøya ⁹⁾	2021 [40] 2022 [40]		0.05/0.01	0.25/0.5	Snow pit, snow probe	0.21/0.23

Flatbreen ¹⁽⁵⁾	20130420 [11.8] 20140405 [12.2] 20150404 [13] 20180426 [22.8]	80 (2013, 2014) 100 (2015) 800 MHz 80.7/1.6GHz 67 (2018)	0.2	0.8-1.5	snow pit, core (GNSS, RTK GNSS)	0.21
Fuglebekken ¹⁾	20160419 [12.3] 20160519 [3.7]	61	0.2 (20160419), 0.1 (20160519)	0.85 (20160419), 0.1 (20160519)	snow probe, fixed snow gauges (RTK GNSS)	0.22 (20160419), 0.18 (20160519)
Fuglebekken ⁵⁾	20220429 [8]	67	0.2	0.5	snow probe/ fixed snow gauges (GNSS)	
Fugleberget ⁵⁾	20220505 [1.6]	67	0.2		snow probe (GNSS)	
Fuglebergsletta ¹⁾	20160430 [10.3]	45	0.2	0.85	snow probe (RTK GNSS)	0.22
Hansbreen ¹⁾	20080426 [63.9], 20110414 [117.5] 20130416 [105.1] 20140403 [103.9] 20140412 [25.9] 20150402 [98.5] 20150511 [78.1] 20150608 [44.5] 20160418 [91.1] 20170420-22 [105.1] 20180418 [105.1] 20190406 [105] 20220407 [94.9]	80 (2014, 2017, 2018), 99 (2015)	0.2	1.0-1.5	snow pit, core, ablation stakes (RTK GNSS)	
Hansbreen ⁵⁾	20180418 [105.1] 20190406 []	67	0.2	1.2	snowpit (RTK GNSS)	
Holtedahlfonna ⁸⁾	20180324 [22.2]	83	0.2		snowpit (GNSS)	
Isbjornhamna ¹⁾	20150423 [0.7]	100	0.2	0.2	snow probe (RTK GNSS)	
Kongsvegen ³⁾	199605					
Kongsvegen ⁹⁾	2016	-	-	-		-
Lomonosovfonna ³⁾	20120413 [49] 20140403 [35] 20160409 [49] 20170425 [35]	155	0.5	1.5	snow pit, core (RTK GNSS)	average 0.20
Longyearbreen ⁸⁾	20180401 [8.2]	83	0.2		snow pit (GNSS)	
lower Bayelva catchment ⁷⁾	1997/1998 [1.5x2]					
Maritbreen-Philipbreen ⁸⁾	20170327 [15.4]	83	0.2		snow pit (GNSS)	

Survey area and coordinates	Date of the survey (YYYY-MM-DD) and total distance [km]	Time window [ns]	Trace-to-trace time interval [s]	Average trace-to-trace distance interval [m]	Snow depth validation method (Positioning mode)	Snow RWV applied [m, ns]
Nannbreen ¹⁾	20130516 [20.1]	80	0.2	1.0-1.5	snow pit (RTK GNSS)	0.21
Recherchebreen ¹⁾	20160412	80	0.2	-	snow pi, core (GNSS)	-
Recherchebreen, Nathorstbreen, Doktorbreen, Polakkbreen, Strong-Nuiddbreen, Morsjnevubreen, Grenfjordbreen, Slakbreen, Ulvebreen, Kongsvegen, Mittag-Lefflerbreen, Kvitbreen, Hannabreen, Raufjordbreen, Asgardfonna, Valhallsfonna ³⁾⁴⁾⁷⁾	1997-1999	-	-	-	snow pit, snow probe	-
Renardbreen ¹⁾	20080402 [37]	-	-	1.5-2	snow pit (RTK GNSS)	0.21
Revdalen ¹⁾	20160421 [21.6]	45	0.2	0.75	snow probe (RTK GNSS)	0.22
Revdalen ⁵⁾	20160421 [15.7]	67	0.2	0.75	snow probe, snow pit (GNSS)	0.22
Slakbreen ⁴⁾	1997	-	-	-	snow pit	-
Slakbreen ⁸⁾	20180303	83	0.2	-	snow pit (GNSS)	-
Storebreen ¹⁾	20130420 [12.3] 20140405 [15.7] 20140413 [15.7] 20150404 [13] 20180426 [19.7]	100 (2015), 80 (2013-2014, 2018)	0.2	1.0-1.5	snow pit (RTK GNSS)	0.21
Storebreen ⁵⁾	20180426 [19.7]	67	0.2	1.2	snow pit (RTK GNSS)	-
Vestfonna ¹⁾	20090518 20090519 [90]	-	-	1.5-2	(RTK GNSS)	0.21
Werenskioldbreen ¹⁾	20130515 [57.9] 20140520 [47.7] 20150407 [51.2] 20150515 [52.5]	80 (2013, 2014 100 (2015))	0.2	1.0-1.5	snow pit (RTK GNSS)	0.21
Wilczekodden ¹⁾	20150423 [0.92]	100	0.2	0.2	snow probe (RTK GNSS)	-

- 1) MALÅ RAMAC survey system, 800 MHz shielded antenna
- 2) MALÅ RAMAC survey system, 200 MHz unshielded antenna
- 3) MALÅ RAMAC survey system, 500 MHz shielded antenna
- 4) PulseEKKO (450 MHz)
- 5) MALÅ ProEx survey system, 1.6 GHz shielded antenna
- 6) PulseEKKO PRO (500 MHz)
- 7) GSSI SIR System 2 (500 MHz)
- 8) MALÅ ProEx survey system, 800 MHz shielded antenna
- 9) GNSS Sir-4000

Appendix 2

The data in the repository include parameters such as survey metadata (.csv) and GPX tracks (.shp).

Metadata access: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7298986>.

Dataset Name and Survey Date	GNSS coordinate system	Location	Dataset provider
20060421-27_Amundsenisen_UoS 20110416_Amundsenisen_UoS 20130505_Amundsenisen_UoS	UTM: 33X E511271 N8582040	Amundsenisen	Mariusz Grabiec, Michał Laska, Dariusz Ignatiuk, University of Silesia in Katowice
20140520_Ariebreen_UoS	UTM: 33X E512305 N8549887	Ariebreen	Michał Laska, University of Silesia in Katowice
1999_Austfonna_UiO 2004_Austfonna_UiO 2005_Austfonna_UiO 2006_Austfonna_UiO 2007_Austfonna_UiO 2008_Austfonna_UiO 2009_Austfonna_UiO 2010_Austfonna_UiO 2011_Austfonna_UiO 2012_Austfonna_UiO 2013_Austfonna_UiO 2014_Austfonna_UiO 2015_Austfonna_UiO 2016_Austfonna_UiO 2017_Austfonna_UiO 2018_Austfonna_UiO	UTM: 35X E448113 N8851524	Austfonna	Trond Eiken, Andrea Taurisano, University of Oslo, Thorben Dunse, Western Norway University of Applied Sciences, Kjetil Melvold, NVE
202104_Brøggerhalvøya_NPI 202204_Brøggerhalvøya_NPI	UTM: 33X E431531 N8761203	Brøggerhalvøya	Jean-Charles Gallet, The Norwegian Polar Institute
20130420_Flatbreen_UoS 20140405_Flatbreen_UoS 20150404_Flatbreen_UoS 20180426_Flatbreen_UoS	UTM: 33X E544763 N8564598	Flatbreen	Mariusz Grabiec, Michał Laska, Dariusz Ignatiuk, Barbara Barzycka, University of Silesia in Katowice
20160419_Fuglebekken_IGPAS 20160519_Fuglebekken_IGPAS 20220429_Fuglebekken_IGPAS	UTM: 33X E513703 N8547766	Fuglebekken	Bartłomiej Luks, Daniel Kępski, Institute of Geophysics, Mariusz Grabiec, University of Silesia in Katowice
20220505_Fugleberget_IGPAS	UTM: 33X E513459 N8548511	Fugleberget	Bartłomiej Luks, Institute of Geophysics
20160430_Fuglebergsletta_IGPAS	UTM: 33X E511847 N8547841	Fuglebergsletta	Bartłomiej Luks, Daniel Kępski, Institute of Geophysics, Aleksander Uszczyk, University of Silesia in Katowice

Dataset Name and Survey Date	GNSS coordinate system	Location	Dataset provider
20080426_Hansbreen_UoS 201104_14_17_Hansbreen_UoS 20130416_Hansbreen_UoS 20140403_12_Hansbreen_UoS 20140521_Hansbreen_UoS 20150402_Hansbreen_UoS 20150511_Hansbreen_UoS 20150608_Hansbreen_UoS 20160418_Hansbreen_UoS 20170420_Hansbreen_UoS 20170422_Hansbreen_UoS 20180418_Hansbreen_UoS 20190406_Hansbreen_UoS 20220407_Hansbreen_UoS	UTM: 33X E515758 N8552524	Hansbreen	Mariusz Grabiec, Michał Laska, Dariusz Ignatiuk, Aleksander Uszczyk, University of Silesia in Katowice
20180324_Holtedahlfonna_IGPAS	33X E468703 N8777705	Holtedahlfonna	Bartłomiej Luks, Institute of Geophysics, Polish Academy of Sciences
20150423_Isbjornhamna_UoS_IGPAS	UTM: 33X E514142 N8547348	Isbjornhamna	Michał Laska, University of Silesia in Katowice, Mateusz Moskalik, Institute of Geophysics, Polish Academy of Sciences
2016_Kongsvegen_NPI	UTM: 33X E451639 N8750747	Kongsvegen	Jack Kohler, The Norwegian Polar Institute
20120413_Lomonosovfonna_UU 20140403_Lomonosovfonna_UU 20160409_Lomonosovfonna_UU 20170409_Lomonosovfonna_UU	UTM: 33X E553500 N874900	Lomonosovfonna	Rickard Pettersson, Uppsala University
20180401_Longyearbreen_IGPAS	UTM: 33X E511284 N8678070	Longyearbreen	Bartłomiej Luks, Institute of Geophysics, Polish Academy of Sciences
20180327_Maritbreen_Philipbreen_IGPAS	33X E563357 N8711448	Maritbreen_ Philipbreen	Bartłomiej Luks, Institute of Geophysics, Polish Academy of Sciences
20130516_Nannbreen_UoS	UTM: 33X E507990 N8562080	Nannbreen	Michał Laska, Dariusz Ignatiuk University of Silesia in Katowice
20160412_Recherchebreen_UoS	UTM: 33X E495438 N8596043	Recherchebreen	Mariusz Grabiec, University of Silesia in Katowice
20080402_Renardbreen_UoS	UTM: 33X E484754 N8603965	Renardbreen	Mariusz Grabiec, University of Silesia in Katowice
20160421_Revdalen_IGPAS 20220428_Revdalen_IGPAS	UTM: 33X E510145 N8548676	Revdalen	Bartłomiej Luks, Daniel Kępski, Institute of Geophysics, Aleksander Uszczyk, University of Silesia in Katowice
20180330_Slakbreen_IGPAS	33X E534707 N8657094	Slakbreen	Bartłomiej Luks, Institute of Geophysics, Polish Academy of Sciences
20130420_Storbreen_UoS 20140405_Storbreen_UoS 20140413_Storbreen_UoS 20150404_Storbreen_UoS 20180426_Storbreen_UoS	UTM: 33X E532903 N8563265	Storbreen	Mariusz Grabiec, Michał Laska, Dariusz Ignatiuk, Barbara Barzycka, University of Silesia in Katowice
20090518_19_Vestfonna_UoS	UTM: 34X E600178 N8878889	Vestfonna	Mariusz Grabiec, University of Silesia in Katowice

Dataset Name and Survey Date	GNSS coordinate system	Location	Dataset provider
20130513_Werenskioldbreen_UoS 20140520_Werenskioldbreen_UoS 20150407_Werenskioldbreen_UoS 20150515_Werenskioldbreen_UoS	UTM: 33X E509683 N8554672	Werenskioldbreen	Michał Laska, Dariusz Ignatiuk, Mariusz Grabiec University of Silesia in Katowice
20150423_Wilczekodden_UoS_IGPAS	UTM: 33X E513446 N8546554	Wilczekodden	Michał Laska, University of Silesia in Katowice, Mateusz Moskalik, Institute of Geophysics, Polish Academy of Sciences
1997_WintherSand_UiO 1998_WintherSand_UiO 1999_WintherSand_UiO	-	Svalbard	Jan Gunnar Winther, Knut Sand, University of Oslo